

EUPHRESCO-II

FINAL DISSEMINATION CONFERENCE

AND

LAUNCH OF THE LONG-TERM

EUPHRESCO NETWORK

Main Conference Day – Wednesday 26TH March 2014

08:15-08:45	Arrive, Registration and Coffee
SESSION 1	EUPHRESCO: Why, What and How? - Session Chair: Elspeth Steel, UK
08:45–09:00	Welcome Address Emmanuelle Soubeyran, Head of French Plant Health Service
09:00–09:30	Challenges for Plant Health and the need for research Robert Baayen, The European Commission, DG SANCO
09:30–09:50	Introduction to EUPHRESCO Alan Inman, EUPHRESCO Coordinator
09:50-10:20	Trans-national research ... “Learning by doing” EUPHRESCO in Action Eric Regouin (IEZ, NL) and Sylvia Blumel (AGES, AT) Discussion , as required
10:20–10:50	BREAK – Tea/coffee

SESSION 2 PERSPECTIVES ON EUPHRESCO - Session Chair: Sylvia Blümel, Austria	
10:50–11:10	<p>Experiences, Perspectives, Impacts and Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>An ‘Old’ Partner’s Perspective (from 2006-2014), Jens Unger, Germany</i> • <i>A ‘New’ Partner’s Perspective (from 2011-2014), Leonor Cruz, Portugal</i>
11:10–12:10	<p>Experiences, Perspectives, Impacts and Outcomes: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A Researcher’s Perspective, Neil Boonham, UK</i> • <i>A Researcher’s Perspective, Steen Lykke Nielsen, Denmark</i> • <i>A Researcher’s Perspective, Geraldine Anthoine, France</i> • <i>Wider European Perspectives, Natalia Sherokolava, Russia</i>
12:10–13:00	<p>Experiences, Perspectives, Impacts and Outcomes: Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>EPPO perspectives</i> Françoise Petter, EPPO • <i>EFSA Perspectives</i> Giuseppe Stancanelli, EFSA, Plant Health • <i>EUPHRESCO Evaluation and Impact Analysis</i> Stephen Hunter and Laura Meagher <p>Panel Discussion (led by Chair) with all Session-2 Speakers</p>
13:00–15:00	LUNCH AND POSTERS (AND INFORMAL NETWORKING)
SESSION 3 THE FUTURE FOR EUPHRESCO - Session Chair: Stephen Hunter, UK	
15:00-16:00	<p>Plant Health Research Coordination and the Future Research Landscape Silke Steinmöller, Germany</p> <p>Facilitated Discussion (led by Chair)</p>
16:00-16:30	<p>The Future – EUPHRESCO and EPPO Martin Ward, EPPO Director</p> <p>Reflections on EUPHRESCO-I and II and Future Prospects for the long-term, sustainable EUPHRESCO Network</p>
16:30–17:00	<p>Final Reflections (All - Led by Chair, EUPHRESCO and EPPO) and Information for Evening Activities (EUPHRESCO-2 Project Office)</p>
18:30	Drinks Reception
19:30	Conference Dinner